

COMPARISON OF C-PLY™ SP (THIN PLY) WITH WOVEN FABRIC AND UD PERFORMANCES

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ABSTRACT

Chomarat has specialized in textile reinforcements for several decades. More recently we have worked with Pr. Stephen Tsai from Stanford University and Pr. Sung Ha from Hanyang University to develop new non-crimp fabrics, called C-Ply™ with thin plies and shallow angles. High quality thin plies are made using a tow spreading technology to spread standard modulus (HS) and intermediate modulus (IM) carbon tows. In addition, C-Ply™ tape offers a significant time savings in terms of machine utilization.

In this study we focused on 0/45° and 0/30° bi-angle stitched fabrics made from HS carbon fiber. We tested open hole tension, un-notched tension, compression and compression after impact properties of composite panels manufactured with C-Ply™ pre-impregnated with epoxy resin. These results were compared with those of a woven fabric and a unidirectional tape; which are standard textile reinforcements already qualified for aerospace applications.

As expected quasi-isotropic composites manufactured with C-Ply™ show good mechanical properties both in notched and un-notched tension and compression tests. The obtained values are very close and even higher than plain weave fabric and UD. This can be explained by the effect of thin ply which is known to improve mechanical performances by limiting micro-cracking and delamination damage and by the effect of crimp which reduces carbon fiber mechanical properties of woven fabric. These results corroborate the results given in the literature by Pr. Tsai [1], composites manufactured with C-Ply™ based on shallow angle show considerably higher performances thanks to off axis angles of 30 and -30°.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fibre reinforced laminated composite parts are used in many structural applications with high requirements such as aeronautics, aerospace and automotive thanks to their high mechanical properties and the weight saving compared to standard materials like metals. The increasing demand of composite materials in these industries requires improving material production with more efficient methods to reduce time and cost but keeping and even improving mechanical performance.

C-Ply™, the brand name for Chomarat's carbon non-crimp fabric (NCF) is a patent pending invention by Stanford University and Chomarat that offers significant weight and cost reduction [1]. This project is mobilizing companies and universities joint teams from around the world to test and develop the advantages of C-Ply™. The combining of multiple layers in a single NCF addresses the time and cost saving issues. The spreading technology used for C-Ply™ uses larger filament count tows to create thin plies which is cheaper than the 1K or 3K fibre typically used to produce light textile reinforcement. The multiple number "sub-ply" in a single C-Ply™ reduces the laying time of automated tape laying machine by laying two directions simultaneously.

In laminated composites, the typical causes of damage are micro-cracking, delamination and fibre breakage which can be initiated by weaknesses like material defects or damages made to allow the assembly of the composite parts [2]. The aim of this study is to compare the mechanical properties of C-Ply™ with different lay-up stacking sequences against other kinds of textile reinforcements that are already qualified for aerospace applications.

2 C-PLY™ CONSTRUCTION

NCFs are very different from other kinds of textile reinforcement constructions. Their simple assembly, high quality, uniformity and good mechanical performance make them attractive. NCFs are preferred over woven fabrics because, as the name suggests, NCFs don't add crimp to the fibres. The absence of crimp enhances in-plane mechanical properties of NCFs when compared to woven fabrics. The construction of NCFs is also more flexible than woven material. Standard woven material has equal amounts of fibre in the warp (0°) and weft (90°), but NCFs can have up to four layers of fibres and each of them at a unique angle. Chomarat can provide a wide range of NCFs from thin ply to thick ply by using different carbon fibre types and our spreading technology to vary the individual layer weights. C-Ply™ is constructed by stacking the individual layers (maximum of 4) at the correct orientation (from -20° to +20° and 0°) and then stitching the layers to maintain position and to permit handling.

Weight saving continues to be a challenge and many industries and universities are carrying out research to spread large carbon fibres tows to produce increasingly lighter tapes [3]. In this study we will focus on NCFs made from spread tow carbon fibre.

Typical light textile reinforcement uses expensive 1K or 3K carbon fibres, but with spread tow technology, it is now possible to make high quality tapes that are thinner and lighter than 1K or 3K from tows that are larger than 12K.

Figure 1 shows how different tow sizes and grades can be used to produce different tape weights from 50 to 300gsm/ply with big tow such as 12K and higher.

Figure 1. Chomarat's range of C-Ply™ SP

Chomarat uses Karl Mayer/Liba's tow spreading technology to achieve ultra-light tapes [4]. Conventional carbon tows are spread by routing yarns over and under several bars half of which are fixed and half vibrate. The back and forth movement opens the tows and spreads filaments to join the adjacent yarn filaments. The goal is to obtain a high quality light tape that is as thin as possible with consistent uniformity in width and thickness and enough cohesion between tows.

Once the tape is produced, it is placed on the conveyor belt of the multiaxial knitting machine. The tape is unwound, cut and placed at the selected orientation; which can be balanced angles (+/-45°) or unbalanced (ψ°/ϕ°) with the off-axis angles as shallow as 20°. Standard C-Ply™ is a bi-angle NCF but Chomarat is able to provide NCF made from one up to four plies depending on the application.

Figure 2. Tapes laying - C-Ply™ before stitching

The off-axis angle can be used as a design variable to optimize performance. The purpose of the shallow angles is to make a laminate much stronger in a specified direction and to decrease delamination and impact damage by reducing the angles between plies. C-Ply™ can be designed to optimize fibre performance [1].

The final step is to combine the different layers with a very light stitching. The stitching yarn keeps the fibre in the correct orientation and allows the fabric to be manipulated without falling apart. The stitching can be applied in a variety of patterns to improve physical and mechanical properties. Combining multiple layers with stitching offers a significant time savings when used in either automated tape laying machines, or hand lay-up processes. It increases the speed and productivity by laying several plies at once instead of the traditional method of apply a single ply at a time.

3 EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

The experimental program was conducted in 2 phases. The first phase compared the mechanical properties of thin ply laminates using only C-Ply™ materials, but varying the fibre angle. The second phase compared the mechanical performance of the C-Ply™ to standard materials already qualified for aerospace applications.

3.1 MATERIALS

The C-Ply™ produced by Chomarat was constructed using Toray's high strength carbon fibre T700SC 12K 50C 800tex carbon tows. The tows were spread from an initial nominal width of 6mm to a width of 11mm to make a tape that was 10inch wide and 0.07mm thick with a nominal areal weight of 75gsm. Then spread tapes were placed on the multi-axial knitting machine to produce the following material used in this study:

- C-Ply™ 0/-45° 150 CT3,4 12K HS : (A)
- C-Ply™ 0/+30° 150 CT3,4 12K HS : (B)
- C-Ply™ 0/-30° 150 CT3,4 12K HS : (C)

These materials were then pre-impregnated with Cytec's MTM45-1 epoxy resin system.

Table 1. Materials specification

Name	Fiber	Resin	Thickness	FAW	Lay-up	FVF
C-Ply™ 0/-45°	Toray T700S 12K 50C	Cytec MTM 45-1	0,14 mm	148 gsm	[0/-45, 90/45] ₁₂ Quasi-isotropic	57,1 %
C-Ply™ 0±/30°	Toray T700S 12K 50C	Cytec MTM 45-1	0,14 mm	149 gsm	[0/30, 0/-30] ₁₂ Anisotropic	57,9 %

Fiber volume fraction was approximately 57% and the values were determined by matrix digestion method according to ASTM Standard D3171-09 [7].

C-Ply™ 0/-45° and C-Ply™ 0/±30° were made from the same fibre tows but with two different lay-up sequences. The first one, C-Ply™ 0/-45° is composed of the NCF (A) and the second one, C-Ply™ 0/±30° is composed of the NCFs (B) and (C), shallow angles. Panels made from C-Ply™ 0/-45° were fabricated in quasi-isotropic layup [0/-45/90/45]₁₂ (25/50/25) where the three numbers in parentheses represent the percentage of 0°, +/-45° and 90° plies respectively and the “12” after layup sequence represent the number of repetitions in the layup. Laminated composites made from C-Ply™ 0/±30° were fabricated in anisotropic layup [0/30/0/-30]₁₂ (50/25/25) where the three numbers in parentheses represent the percentage of 0°, +30° and -30° plies respectively.

The C-Ply™ used in this study isn't the thinnest C-Ply™ possible but it can be considered a thin ply because the areal weight of 75gsm is lighter than the standard 134gsm.

Figure 3. Cross section of the laminates based on C-Ply™

3.2 MATERIAL CHARACTERIZATION

Material characterization tests were conducted on the two C-Ply™ laminates with the different lay-up sequences to test their mechanical performance. The characterization tests consisted of open-hole tension, un-notched tension, as well as compression and compression after impact. The un-notched tests were completed to characterize the tensile and compression strength of both panels. The open-hole tests were completed to observe the effect a hole in the specimen had on the laminate performance. The compression after impact tests were completed to observe the reduction of compression strength after the laminates sustained impact damage.

The testing was conducted at the National Institute for Aviation Research (NIAR), a university-based aviation research center in the USA that provides research, design, testing, certification and training to the aviation manufacturing industries and government agencies ... [5]. In order to get an accurate comparison with other materials, NIAR normalized the test values based on the cured ply thickness (CPT) to reduce the variability of the fibre-dominated material properties [6]. The average value is calculated from 5 replications.

$$\text{Normalized Value} = \text{Test Value} \times \frac{\text{CPT}_{\text{specimen}}}{\text{CPT}_{\text{normalizing}}} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{CPT}_{\text{specimen}} = \frac{\text{Average Sample Thickness}}{\text{Number of plies}} \quad (2)$$

3.2.1 Un-Notched Tension : UNT

The un-notched tension was tested in accordance with the ASTM Standard D3039 [8]. The width of the specimen was 25.4 mm, the length was 254mm and the thickness was 3.4mm. The test specimens from the quasi-isotropic panel made with the C-Ply™ 0/-45° were cut and tested in 0 degree direction. The test specimens from the anisotropic panel made with the C-Ply™ 0/±30° were cut and tested in both the 0 and 90 degree directions.

Figure 4. Shallow angles – Anisotropic lay-up sequence

The C-Ply™ 0/-45° is a quasi-isotropic laminate, there are the same percentage of plies oriented at 0 degrees and 90 degrees thus the tests in either direction would give the same result. Whereas the laminate with the C-Ply™ 0/±30° is an anisotropic laminate made from carbon layers oriented at 0 and 30 degrees and the testing in 0 and 90 degree directions will be different. At 0 degree, all the carbon fibres will be loaded, even the off-axis layers because they are partially aligned to load direction. However, during the 90 degree testing the fibres will be at 60 and 90 degrees compared to the main load and matrix cracking can occur very quickly. We can predict that results will be lower than C-Ply™ 0/-45° and C-Ply™ 0/±30° tested in 0 degrees.

Table 2. Un-notched Tension properties

	C-Ply™ 0/-45°	C-Ply™ 0/±30° : 0°	C-Ply™ 0/±30° : 90°
Average UNT Strength Normalized (MPa)	885.81	1664.43	150.40
CV%	2.36	1.36	0.31
Average UNT Modulus Normalized (MPa)	46.69	84.63	11.07
CV%	1.32	0.90	0.47

The UNT test was conducted on five specimens from each materials and we feel confident that results are representative and repeatable because coefficients of variation are under 3%.

As expected the tests conducted at 0 degrees show better results for C-Ply™ 0/±30°; twice as high as the standard quasi-isotropic laminate made of C-Ply™ 0/-45°. That can be explained because the 90 degree plies have been eliminated, the 0 degree plies have been doubled and the off-axis plies are biased toward the main ([0°/30°/0°/-30°]₁₂).

When we observed the test results on C-Ply™ 0/±30° at 0 and 90 degrees, as expected, 90 degrees results are very low. There are no fibres in load direction, therefore only the matrix is loaded and micro-cracks occurs between carbon fibres.

Shallow angles were developed for use in parts that are highly loaded in a single direction with minimal off-axis strength required.

Figure 5. Fibers at 90° compared to main load

3.2.2 Un-Notched Compression : UNC

The un-notched compression tests were performed in accordance with the ASTM Standard D6641 [9]. The width of the specimen was 12.7mm, the length was 140mm and the thickness was 3.4mm.

Similar to the UNT test the un-notched compression tests were done in one direction on the quasi-isotropic panel and tested in both the 0 and 90 directions of the anisotropic panel.

Table 3. Un-notched Compression properties

	C-Ply™ 0/-45°	C-Ply™ 0/±30° : 0°	C-Ply™ 0/±30° : 90°
Average UNC Strength Normalized (MPa)	580.00	758.31	274.18
CV%	2.30	2.84	0.63
Average UNC Modulus Normalized (MPa)	43.01	78.69	11.07
CV%	1.83	1.37	0.79

The C-Ply™ UNC results seem to be repeatable with a coefficient of variation under 3%. The C-Ply™ 0/±30° tested at 0 degrees shows better results than C-Ply™ 0/-45° but the improvement is less than UNT properties. When we compare C-Ply™ 0/±30° tested at 0 and 90 degrees we can see a similar pattern to the UNT testing.

3.2.3 Open-Hole Tension : OHT

The open-hole tension testing was in accordance with ASTM Standard D5766 [10]. The width of the specimen was 38.1 mm, the length was 305mm and the thickness was 3.4mm. The hole diameter was 6.4mm; the ratio of the width of the specimen to diameter of the hole is equal to 6. NIAR conducted the tests on the two materials C-Ply™ 0/-45° and C-Ply™ 0/±30° cutting in 0 degree direction.

It is still common practice to attach composite laminates with mechanical fasteners and therefore the open hole test is used to observe the effect of notches on the behaviour of composite laminate. The hole drilled in the middle of the specimen is like a defect which cuts the continuous carbon fibres, decreasing the mechanical properties of the laminate. It can also initiate damage like delamination or micro-cracking during loading.

Table 4. Open Hole Tension properties

	C-Ply™ 0/-45°	C-Ply™ 0/±30°
Average OHT Strength Normalized (MPa)	433.71	681.08
CV%	0.93	2.14

As expected, the OHT values are lower than UNT because the hole weakens the laminate; their values are about two times lower. The strength decrease comparison is based on the hole factor analysis.

$$\text{Hole Factor} = \frac{\text{OHT}}{\text{UNT}} \quad (3)$$

Table 5. Hole factor - Tension

	C-Ply™ 0/-45°	C-Ply™ 0/±30°
Hole Factor OHT/UNT	0.49	0.41

The hole factor of the C-Ply™ 0/±30° is lower than the C-Ply™ 0/-45° because UNT results were quite high and the reduction of strength due to the hole is significant. The good results in UNT can be explained by the continuous carbon fibres along the load axis and slight off-axis shallow angles while in OHT test, all fibres close to the load directions are discontinuous. The hole factor of the C-Ply™ 0/-45° shows that OHT strength is exactly half of UNT strength.

3.2.4 Open-Hole Compression : OHC

The open-hole compression test was performed in accordance with ASTM Standard D6484 [11]. The specimen width was 38.1mm, the length was 305mm and the thickness was 3.4mm. The hole diameter was 6.4mm; the ratio of the width of the specimen to diameter of the hole is equal to 6. NIAR conducted the test on the two C-PlyTM0/-45° and C-PlyTM0/±30° materials by cutting the specimens in 0 degree direction. It is interesting to observe the variation of notched composite laminate behaviour in compression compared to un-notched materials.

Table 6. Open Hole Compression properties

	C-Ply TM 0/-45°	C-Ply TM 0/±30°
Average OHC Strength Normalized (MPa)	307.60	366.66
CV%	2.55	3.06

As in OHT test, OHC strength of C-PlyTM 0/-45° and C-PlyTM 0/±30° are about half of UNC values and C-PlyTM 0/±30° still has the best results. The hole factor shows how the strength is reduced because of the notch.

Table 7. Hole factor - Compression

	C-Ply TM 0/-45°	C-Ply TM 0/±30°
Hole Factor OHC/UNC	0.53	0.48

Hole factors in compression are higher than in the tension test and as similar to the previous tests the C-PlyTM 0/±30° shows better UNC and OHC than the C-PlyTM 0/-45° but the hole factor of the latter is higher.

3.2.5 Compression After Impact : CAI

The compression after impact testing was performed in accordance with ASTM Standard D7137 [13]. The specimen width was 102mm, the length was 152mm and the thickness was 4.5mm. This test was performed in three steps. Firstly, all specimens are impacted at 30J (1500 in.lb/in) in accordance with ASTM Standard D7136 [12], the damage area is recorded and then the impacted specimens are compression tested.

Compression after impact is one of the most important test in aeronautics because structural component can be damaged during manufacture, assembly, and maintenance. For example tools falling during maintenance or debris which impact the plane during take-off, landing or flight can cause impact damage to the laminated structures. Thus it is important to know the residual strength of impacted laminates.

Table 8. Compression After Impact properties

	C-Ply TM 0/-45°	C-Ply TM 0/±30°
Area of delamination (mm²)	1903	2379
Average CAI Strength Normalized (MPa)	207.69	272.22
CV%	2.03	2.20

The area of delamination was measured after a 30J impact. The values are quite high, around 2000 mm², which means that the specimens impacted are unstable and have high variability thus we could expected poor CAI values. But when we observe CAI normalized values, we can say that they are not so bad.

4 DISCUSSION

4.1 C-Ply™ 0/-45° vs. C-Ply™ 0/±30°

This study was conducted to investigate C-Ply™ performances and observe the difference between standard quasi-isotropic laminated panels and non-conventional anisotropic panels. For this purpose, two thin ply laminated composites panels were made using the same carbon fibres, areal weight, thickness, fibre content, and resin matrix system. The only differences was the fibre orientation in the lay-up sequence. These laminates were then tested to observe differences in the following areas: un-notched tension, un-notched compression, open-hole tension, open-hole compression and compression after impact.

All strength results previously described are summarized in the figure 6. C-Ply™ 0/-45° is considered as the reference to be compared with C-Ply™ 0/±30°.

Figure 6. Comparison between C-Ply™ 0/-45° and C-Ply™ 0/±30°

Un-notched laminates based on C-Ply™ 0/±30° tested at 90° show very low results because only matrix is loaded and there is no fibre in main load direction.

It is really interesting to compare the C-Ply™ 0/-45° and C-Ply™ 0/±30° performance when the load is in warp direction. We can see that C-Ply™ 0/±30° generally shows better performance but the improvements generated by shallow angle aren't equal for all tests.

- Variation between the two C-Ply™ is higher in tension than in compression for un-notched and notched laminates.
- Improvements due to the shallow angles are around 20-30% in compression (UNC, OHC and CAI tests)
- Improvement due to the shallow angles is higher on un-notched laminates than notched laminates and therefore the C-Ply™ 0/±30° hole factor is lower than C-Ply™ 0/-45°.

In this study, shallow angles show that their purpose is to make a laminate much stronger in the direction of the loaded axis.

4.2 C-Ply™ vs. other textiles reinforcements

The second target of this study was to compare C-Ply™ with two different kinds of constructions: one woven fabric and one UD that are already qualified for aeronautics. We decided to focus on fibre grade, high strength carbon fibres required and areal weight, around 150gsm to be as close as possible of C-Ply™ physical characteristics.

Table 9. Materials specification [14], [15]

Name	Carbon fibre	Construction	Areal weight
PW	Toho Tenax HTS40 3K	Plain Weave	189 gsm
UD	Toray T700G 12K	UD	150 gsm

This selection allows us to compare three different constructions, one non crimp fabric, one woven fabric and one unidirectional tape which are the 3 textile reinforcements most used in composite materials.

The table 10 gathers performances of those three kinds of reinforcements. All values were normalized by cured ply thickness (1) and (2) because the fibre volume fraction of all materials was not identical. The fibre volume content of composite laminates based on C-PlyTM is 57%, based on woven fabric is 55% and based on unidirectional tape is 54%.

Table 10. Strength of C-PlyTM, PW and UD [14], [15]

Properties	C-Ply TM 0/-45°	PW	UD
UNT (MPa)	885.81	664.72	676.99
UNC (MPa)	580.00	510.50	548.76
OHT (MPa)	433.71	359.59	348.15
OHC (MPa)	307.60	287.55	276.45
HF : Tens.	0.49	0.54	0.51
HF : Comp.	0.53	0.56	0.50
CAI (MPa)	207.69	233.29	NA

Figure 7. Comparison between C-PlyTM, PW and UD

C-PlyTM normalized data in un-notched and notched tension and compression are higher than woven fabric and UD. These results can be explained by the construction and the physical properties of each kind of material. C-PlyTM is a non crimp fabric so as its name suggests fibres are aligned without any crimp unlike woven fabric where yarns have slight crimp due to the weave. Crimp decreases the mechanical properties of the carbon fibre and can explain the lower results. Concerning the strength decrease due to the notch, C-PlyTM hole factors are lower than woven fabric. It may be explained by the interlacing between warp and weft yarns in the woven fabric which can prevent damage propagation initiated by the hole drilled in the middle of the specimen.

Concerning UD, carbon fibres are aligned like C-PlyTM but the difference can be explain by another physical characteristics, the areal weight and as consequence the ply thickness. UD is twice as thick as the C-PlyTM. C-PlyTM is made from two plies of 75gsm each therefore 150gsm total whereas UD is a single ply of 150gsm. Thus the C-PlyTM shows better results than the UD, supporting the theory that thinner plies improve mechanical performances.

As far as CAI is concerned, CAI values from UD are not mentioned in NIAR documents, we can only compare C-PlyTM to PW. CAI data from the C-PlyTM is about 10% lower than the woven fabric. We can assume that the woven fabric specimens were less damaged by the impact and so the residual strength is better but we can't confirm because areas of delamination were not mentioned.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The goal of the study was on one hand to investigate C-PlyTM properties and the shallow angle performances optimization for parts with preferred loading direction and on the other hand to compare C-PlyTM mechanical properties with other kinds of textile reinforcements and more particularly with other materials already qualified for aeronautics.

As expected standard quasi-isotropic laminate based on C-PlyTM performs well in all test configurations with a good repeatability. Very low variations were recorded between all specimens with coefficient of variation lower than 3%.

As expected the anisotropic laminate performed very well when loaded along the direction the fibres and still provided some off axis strength compared to the unidirectional material. The strength values were twice as high as the standard quasi-isotropic un-notched laminate. The results obtained in the study confirm that C-Ply™ with shallow angles can be designed to perform well in composite parts that are highly loaded in one direction.

The study confirms that C-Ply™ is meeting expectations and when compared with woven fabric and unidirectional tape that is already qualified for aeronautics, it shows that C-Ply™ can outperform the current industry standards.

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